

Mechanisms of Working Memory Prioritization: Top-Down vs. Saccadic Preparation

Cristina Romero-Casas^{1,2*}, Jorge San-Segundo^{3*}, Joaquín Macedo-Pascual^{1,2}, Nuria Camuñas², Almudena Capilla³, Claudia Poch^{1,2+}

¹ Centro de Investigación Nebrija en Cognición (CINC), Universidad Nebrija, Madrid, Spain.

² Departamento de Educación, Universidad de Nebrija, Madrid, Spain.

³ Departamento de Psicología Biológica y de la Salud, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain.

*These authors contributed equally.

+ Correspondence to: Claudia Poch; Universidad Nebrija. C. de Sta. Cruz de Marcenado, 27, 28015 Madrid. Email: cpoch@nebrija.es

Abstract

Selective internal attention prioritizes Working Memory (WM) contents according to task demands, a process commonly studied through the retro-cue paradigm. In this paradigm, a cue presented during the WM maintenance period indicates the item to be probed, allowing for voluntary allocation of attentional resources to enhance memory performance. Recent evidence suggests that saccade preparation toward a location occupied by a WM item may also exert an involuntary bias on WM. In the present study, we compared memory performance and neural oscillatory correlates associated with saccade preparation prioritization and with spatial and color retro-cues. Behavioral results showed that, although a slight prioritization was observed in the saccadic condition, it was not comparable to the benefit provided by either type of retro-cue. Neural oscillations offered further insights into the underlying mechanisms of these two forms of WM prioritization. While alpha lateralization revealed a similar pattern across all mnemonic prioritization conditions, supporting a spatial selection mechanism of the prioritized representation, bilateral alpha amplitude decreased in the retro-cue condition compared to the saccadic preparation condition, reflecting a reduction in WM load following the retro-cue. In sum, it appears that multiple mechanisms, based on covert spatial attention and on strategic distribution of attentional resources to non-relevant items, may account for similarities and differences in voluntary and involuntary prioritization. Overall, top-down prioritization provides a greater performance benefit than automatic prioritization driven by saccadic preparation.

Introduction

Working memory (WM) encompasses processes responsible for the retention and temporal manipulation of information that is relevant to future behavior (Gazzaley & Nobre, 2012). Internal selective attention facilitates flexible behavior by prioritizing WM representations that are imminently relevant for the upcoming action (Itti & Koch, 2000). Most of the empirical evidence supporting flexible WM representations have been obtained using the retro-cue paradigm. In these experiments, the relevance of the maintained content is biased by providing an informative cue once the perceptual array is no longer present. Retrospective cues indicate which content is relevant for the test stage, enabling participants to strategically use this information to optimize their performance. Although memory benefits have been observed at the item and the dimensional level (Hajonides et al., 2020; Heuer & Schubö, 2016), most of the research has used retro-cues linked to object representations. There are numerous ways in which the relevance of an item can be retrospectively cued. For example, by providing an arrow spatial cue that explicitly indicates the position of the object to be probed, or by using a feature cue, such as color or shape, which acts as an indicator of the relevant item that matches the feature of the cue (Heuer et al., 2016; Heuer & Rolfs, 2021; Kuo et al., 2009; Panichello & Buschman, 2021; Van Ede, 2020). A robust neurophysiological correlate of item-based prioritization is the retinotopic alpha modulation in occipito-parietal regions, which has been extensively observed following spatial cues, and to a lesser extent, after feature retro-cues (Poch, Capilla, et al., 2017a). This neuronal signature emphasizes the role of spatial attention in modulating internal representations, even when the cue itself is not spatial (Pertzov et al., 2013). According to the premotor theory, item prioritization would be achieved through the sensory biases that the oculomotor system exerts on internal representations, similar to the perceptual benefit for features of upcoming saccade targets in the perceptual domain (C. M. Moore & Egeth, 1998; T. Moore et al., 2003; Van Ede et al., 2019). In fact, a recent study found a gaze bias associated with the retro-cued representation, evidencing the implication of the oculomotor system in WM prioritization (Van Ede et al., 2019). Furthermore, several studies show that, in absence of explicit retro-cues, eye movements programmed during the delay period can determine the contents of visual WM, even when the saccade cue lacked predictive value (Ohl & Rolfs, 2017; Rajsic et al., 2017). It has been proposed that task relevance itself does not impact WM maintenance but rather is a consequence of oculomotor selection of task-relevant locations. A clever experiment found dissociated effects of task relevance, oculomotor selection and saccade execution in WM performance (Hanning & Deubel, 2018). The cited study observed a behavioral benefit for the memory item that matched the saccade preparation target, but not

for the executed saccade target itself nor for the item that was relevant to perform the task but was not a saccade target (Hanning & Deubel, 2018). These findings emphasize the overlapping mechanisms that operate in spatial WM and saccade selection, and they support the proposal that the selection of WM maintained representations is mediated through oculomotor selection.

In contrast to external retro-cues, which provide task relevant information that enables voluntary deployment of resources to enhance performance, the memory bias exerted by saccade preparation is the consequence of oculomotor selection and represents an involuntary bias. Although there are some speculative suggestions regarding their underlying mechanistic equivalency (Heuer et al., 2020), to our knowledge, there has not been a direct comparison between voluntary and involuntary sources of WM selection. In this study, we directly compared the behavior and the oscillatory neural correlates of voluntary and involuntary prioritization in WM. We assessed memory performance across two retro-cue conditions, a spatial retro-cue and a feature retro-cue, as well as in a saccadic preparation condition. The spatial retro-cue was used to match the perceptual cue provided in the saccade preparation task in order to assess alpha power modulations. Since arrow cues have been suggested to trigger exogenous attentional mechanisms due to its perceptual characteristics, we also included a color retro-cue, which is considered to be a pure endogenous cue (Hommel et al., 2001). Although memory advantages and alpha oscillatory modulation have also been found after color retro-cues, a direct comparison between the oscillatory correlates of these two types of retro-cues was yet to be conducted.

Methods

Participants

The present experiment was conducted with a sample of 36 adult participants (mean age, 24.33 years; standard deviation, 4.76; range, 18-38 years), consisting of 20 females and 16 males. All were right-handed according to the Edinburgh Handedness Inventory (Oldfield, 1971). The sample size was determined using G*Power, aiming to detect an effect size of 0.25 and to achieve a statistical power of 0.9. This indicated a minimum sample size of 30 participants (Faul et al., 2007; Macedo-Pascual et al., 2023). Participants signed an informed consent form in accordance with the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki. Exclusion criteria included a history of neurological or psychiatric disorders, family history of epilepsy, and use of psychotropic drugs prior to the experiment.

Experimental task

The experimental tasks are illustrated in Fig 1. Each of the three different conditions was presented in randomized blocks. The structure of the three conditions, based on a retro-cue paradigm, was the same, but differed in the instructions given between the saccadic and the spatial retro-cue conditions, and the physical appearance of the retro-cue between the color and the spatial retro-cue conditions. In the saccadic conditions, participants were instructed to prepare but not execute a saccade in the direction of the cue during the delay period. In the retro-cue condition, participants were told that the retro-cue predicted the probe item. The experiment consisted of a total of 420 trials, distributed in three blocks of 140 trials corresponding to each experimental condition. At the beginning of each block, participants were informed about the characteristics of the stimuli and the task to be performed. The visual stimuli were presented on a screen located at a distance of 60 cm from the participants, ensuring uniformity in the size of the perceived stimuli. The programming and execution of the experiment were carried out using the open-source Psychtoolbox-3 library in MATLAB (Kleiner et al., 2007). Each trial began with the presentation of a fixation point for 1200 ms. Next, a memory set was displayed for 250 ms, consisting of four rectangles with specific orientations that participants had to memorize (0° , 45° , 90° , 135°) and located within a visual angle of 3.8° (Macedo-Pascual et al., 2023). After a maintenance period of 1200 ms, a cue was presented for 200 ms indicating the orientation of the test stimulus in the retro-cue blocks or the direction towards which they had to prepare an eye movement in the saccadic preparation blocks. After a 1200 ms delay period participants were asked to make an orientation judgement on one of the four rectangles in the saccadic conditions, and on the cued item in the retro-cue conditions. The test stimulus was presented for 2000 ms, after which participants had 2000 ms to perform a saccade in the saccadic condition. While in the retro-cue conditions the cue was 100% predictive, in the saccadic conditions the saccadic cue was only congruent with the test item in 25% of the trials. Prioritization comparison between tasks was performed taking into account only congruent trials. In all conditions, the orientation of the test rectangle matched that of the sample rectangle in 50% of the trials, while in the remaining 50% the orientation was randomized. In addition, there was a 25% probability that the retro-cue would point in any of the directions of the presented rectangles.

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the experimental task.

EEG recording

The brain electrical signal was recorded using an ActiChamp system (BrainProducts), equipped with 64 active channels. In addition, electrooculographic (EOG) electrodes were placed to record eye activity, with one horizontal and one vertical electrode, and an external reference electrode was used at the tip of the nose. The data was initially sampled at a rate of 1000 Hz, and a low-pass filter with a cutoff frequency of 100 Hz was applied during acquisition. Subsequently, the data was referenced offline to the tip of the nose and the sampling rate was reduced to 250 Hz using MATLAB and the FieldTrip toolbox (www.fieldtriptoolbox.org). Both preprocessing and subsequent analyses of the electrophysiological signals were carried out using the same FieldTrip toolbox.

Preprocessing and time-frequency analysis

EEG data were preprocessed before analysis, working exclusively with artefact-free data. First, the data were epoched in segments from -2.65 to 2.75 seconds around retro-cue presentation. For the removal of artefacts related to blinks and eye movements (vertical and horizontal), an Independent Component Analysis (ICA) was applied using EEGLAB's 'runica' algorithm, implemented in FieldTrip. Subsequently, individual epochs were visually inspected, discarding those containing obvious artefacts. Channels with excessive noise were identified and interpolated. Oscillatory activity in the alpha band was obtained for each trial by Hilbert transform. Initially, the preprocessed data were filtered in the 8-14 Hz range, and then the time

course of the spectral amplitude of the signal was extracted by calculating the absolute value of the Hilbert transform. Lateralized alpha activity was determined by combining the electrodes from the left retro-cue condition with the mirrored version of the electrodes from the right condition. In this way, contralateral activity was represented at the right electrodes by averaging the right electrodes from the left condition with the left electrodes from the right condition. Similarly, ipsilateral activity was plotted at the left electrodes.

Statistical analysis

Working memory accuracy was assessed using repeated-measures one way ANOVA taking the total percentage of hits on a standardized scale from 0 to 1. Experimental conditions were compared with a statistical significance threshold set at $\alpha = 0.05$. Statistical analysis of alpha oscillatory activity was performed using a non-parametric cluster-based analysis implemented in FieldTrip (Maris & Oostenveld, 2007), designed to control for type I error arising from multiple comparisons. Initially, a parametric statistical test was applied to each electrode-time pair. Subsequently, clusters formed by electrode-time pairs significantly adjacent in temporal or spatial dimensions were identified. For each identified cluster, a cluster statistic was calculated by summing the parametric statistical values within the cluster. Statistical significance was assessed by comparing this statistic with a null distribution, drawn from 10,000 permutations. During each permutation, data were randomly assigned to two subsets, recalculating the maximum cluster statistic for each iteration. The analysis was performed in a 1400 ms time window following cue presentation. At the final stage, the cluster p-value was determined by constructing a histogram of the cluster statistics obtained from the 10,000 permutations, and calculating the proportion of permutations whose statistics exceeded the value observed in the original data.

Results

Memory performance

Memory accuracy was modulated by prioritization condition ($F(2,35) = 33.34$, $p < .001$; eta squared (η^2) = 0.488). While item prioritization was behaviorally equivalent between the two voluntary prioritization conditions, arrow and color retro-cue conditions, ($t(35) = -0.44$, $p = 0.663$; $M_{diff} = -0.004$), they both differed from the saccadic condition ($t(35) = 6.35$, $p < .001$; $M_{diff} = 0.110$; $t(35) = 6.01$, $p < .001$; $M_{diff} = 0.106$ for arrow and color retro-cue, respectively) (Figure 2A). Although performance in congruent saccadic trials and retro-cue trials was not

equivalent, we did find a subtle memory advantage for congruent compared to incongruent trials in the saccadic condition ($t(35) = 2.14, p = .04; d' = 0.35$) (Figure 2B).

The same pattern of results was obtained for Reaction times (RT). RT differed across conditions ($F(2, 35) = 141.48, p < .001; \eta^2 = 0.802$) (Figure 2C). No significant differences in RT were observed between the arrow and color retro-cue conditions ($t(35) = -1.58, p = 0.124; M_{diff} = -0.027$). However, both conditions were performed significantly faster from the saccadic condition ($t(35) = -12.32, p < .001; M_{diff} = -0.327$; $t(35) = -13.98, p < .001; M_{diff} = -0.354$ for the arrow and color retro-cue conditions, respectively). In the saccadic condition we obtained a robust difference between saccadic congruent trials compared to incongruent trials ($t(35) = -5.05, p < .001; d' = -0.84$) (Figure 2D).

Fig. 2. Raincloud plots depicting behavioral performance and reaction times across conditions. Each subplot displays individual data points (cloud of dots), a boxplot, and a one-sided violin plot to illustrate data distribution. **A-** Mean accuracy for color, spatial, and congruent saccadic trials. **B-** Mean accuracy for congruent and incongruent saccadic trials. **C-** Mean reaction times (ms) for color, spatial, and congruent saccadic trials. **D-** Mean reaction times (ms) for congruent and incongruent saccadic trials.

EEG results

After retro-cue presentation, alpha oscillatory activity was significantly lateralized in posterior electrodes in the three conditions. In the arrow retro-cue condition, alpha was significantly lateralized from 250 ms to 920 ms ($p < .001$), in the arrow saccadic condition from 250 to 910 ms ($p < .001$), and in the color retro-cue from 370 ms to 950 ms ($p = .01$). There were no significant differences in alpha lateralization between conditions ($p > .05$) (Figure 3).

Additionally, bilateral alpha power was compared between the two arrow conditions. After the arrow presentation, alpha oscillatory activity was significantly higher in the saccadic condition ($p < .001$) than in the retro-cue condition. This effect was found over the whole scalp, although

more pronounced in posterior-central regions, from 470 ms to 1100 ms (Figure 4).

Fig. 3. Neural dynamics of alpha activity across experimental conditions. The top left display displays the time course of lateralized alpha activity for each condition. Pink shaded brackets highlight time windows with statistically significant lateralized alpha activity. The remaining panels show alpha lateralization as depicted by topoplots, computed as contralateral minus ipsilateral activity. Colored circles indicate electrodes forming the significant cluster.

Fig. 4. Bilateral alpha activity. On the left: Time course of bilateral alpha activity from the electrodes comprising the significant cluster. The pink shaded area highlights the time interval in which statistically significant differences were observed between the saccadic and the spatial retro-cue task. On the right: Topoplot illustrating the difference in bilateral alpha activity between the saccadic and spatial cue conditions. Alpha activity was averaged within the time window corresponding to the significant cluster.

Discussion

Prioritization of WM contents can be based on strategic control of internal attention, but also on involuntary processes such as automatic biases exerted by saccade planning. The current study compared memory performance and alpha oscillatory brain activity in voluntary and involuntary WM prioritization, triggered by a retro-cue and a saccadic cue, respectively. Behavioral results showed that voluntary item prioritization was comparable between the color and the spatial retro-cue conditions. Nevertheless, both showed a clear advantage over the saccadic preparation condition, although there was a slight memory advantage for items congruent with the saccadic preparation target, suggesting that voluntary shifts of attention provide a stronger benefit to WM performance than saccadic preparation. At the neural level, alpha lateralization exhibited the same pattern in the three prioritization conditions, and bilateral posterior alpha oscillatory activity decreased in the spatial retro-cue task compared to the saccade preparation task. In the following, we will argue that these findings suggest that voluntary and involuntary sources of WM prioritization operate through oculomotor selection mechanisms, although voluntary selection might involve more strategic resources related to non-cued representations (Pertsov et al., 2013; Souza et al., 2014).

Memory enhancement for retro-cued items is triggered by top-down mechanisms. However, arrow and color retro-cues might involve different processes. The key difference between these

two types of cues lies in the bottom-up properties of the arrow cue that can additionally induce automatic shifts of spatial attention, while color or feature cues rely on purely endogenous processes. Although there is previous evidence that a feature retro-cue can lead to an item memory advantage similar to the more commonly used spatial retro-cue (Lepsien & Nobre, 2007; Li & Saiki, 2015; Pertzov et al., 2013), some authors have found null effects after other than arrow retro-cues (Berryhill et al., 2012), or more subtle retro-cue benefits after a feature retro-cue (Heuer et al., 2016). These differential effects are believed to have arisen due to methodological aspects such as the short delay between the encoding and the retro-cue. It has been hypothesized that feature retro-cues, such as shape and color, might require additional processing demands taking longer times to be equally effective, as it has been demonstrated in the perceptual domain (Liu et al., 2007). Additional processing might be related to the spatial recoding of the cue in order to apply an internal spatial attentional mechanism as in the spatial retro-cue condition (Pertzov et al., 2013; Poch, Capilla, et al., 2017b). In our study, we used a one-second interval between the encoding and the retro-cue, which has been proven to be long enough to allow for a spatial recoding of the cue. As we will discuss later based on our alpha lateralization results, we propose that retro-cued item prioritization relies on covert shifts of spatial attention under color and spatial cues.

In this context, oculomotor selection would be the mechanism by which covert shifts of spatial attention operate during WM selection, whether in strategic or automatic prioritization (Hanning & Deubel, 2018; Van Ede et al., 2019). However, to our knowledge, a direct comparison between these two types of prioritizations has not yet been made. In our study, we found that involuntary prioritization - based on saccade preparation- was subtle and not equivalent to voluntary prioritization in terms of absolute behavioral performance. In here, the retro-cue was valid in 100% of the trials, allowing participants to adopt a voluntary strategy to improve performance, while saccade targets, in the saccadic condition, did not have predictive value. In this sense, cue reliability has been shown to have an impact on retro-cueing (Gunseli et al., 2015), with two main aspects to consider. First, the lower absolute performance in saccade trials compared to retro-cued trials, and second, the subtle retro-cue benefit observed in those trials. Although the retro-cue effect has been found to occur regardless of cue validity (Berryhill et al., 2012; Dube et al., 2019; Gunseli et al., 2015), there is evidence that high-reliability retro-cues lead to greater retro-cued item enhancement. This effect appears to depend on the validity costs associated with uncued items, as the cost for invalid trials is more pronounced when cue reliability is low. Consequently, the retro-cue effect may result from multiple cognitive mechanisms, depending on how participants adjust their strategic use of resources according to

task demands. While participants prioritize the cue item in both high- and low- reliability trials, in high-reliability trials, non-cued items are dropped from further maintenance, whereas in low-reliability trials, they are still maintained. Similarly, in our study, the saccadic cue was non-predictive, and participants presumably voluntarily allocated equal resources to all items. Although oculomotor selection automatically prioritized the item congruent with the saccade target, compared to incongruent trials, the voluntary maintenance of all items diminished the prioritization benefit compared to retro-cue conditions. This finding is consistent with the spatial attention and WM maintenance alpha oscillatory correlates observed in our results, which will be further elaborated below.

Alpha lateralization results support the idea of functionally equivalent spatial selection mechanisms underlying both involuntary and voluntary prioritization. Alpha lateralization is a well-established correlate of the focus of spatial attention in both the perceptual and mnemonic domains (Capilla et al., 2014; Poch et al., 2014; Thut et al., 2006; Worden et al., 2000), and is believed to be linked to oculomotor control (Popov et al., 2021). As in the perceptual domain, covert shifts of spatial attention within the representation space are driven by the oculomotor system (Van Ede et al., 2019), leading to a gaze bias toward the prioritized representation. Conversely, oculomotor selection during the delay period of a WM task also biases WM performance independently of task relevance (Hanning & Deubel, 2018). In our study, we found a similar alpha lateralization linked to the oculomotor selection: in the saccadic condition, it was associated with the saccade target, and in both retro-cue conditions, it was linked to the selection of the WM representation. These findings suggest that both voluntary prioritization and involuntary prioritization are mediated by oculomotor selection mechanisms responsible for covert shifts of spatial attention. Regarding the mechanisms triggered by arrow and color retro-cues, both induced a similar shift of spatial attention; however, alpha lateralization modulation began around 100 ms later in the color condition, providing further evidence that additional resources are involved in the spatial recoding of the color cue (Keefe & Störmer, 2021; Pertzov et al., 2013; Poch, Capilla, et al., 2017b; Souza & Oberauer, 2016).

Differential mechanisms accounting for the retro-cue effect in voluntary and involuntary prioritization might be further supported by the finding of increased alpha power over posterior-central regions in the saccadic condition compared to the retro-cue condition. Alpha delay activity has been shown to scale with WM load (Heinz & Johnson, 2017; Macedo-Pascual et al., 2019, 2023; Poch et al., 2018; Schroeder et al., 2018; Tuladhar et al., 2007), reflecting increased processing demands or internal directed attention (Benedek et al., 2014; Cooper et al., 2006; Palva & Palva, 2007; Poch, Carretie, et al., 2017; Ray & Cole, 1985). As discussed earlier, high cue

reliability in the retro-cue conditions might have prompted a strategic removal of the non-relevant items, whereas in the saccadic condition non-cued items were still maintained, as indicated by a greater alpha power (Macedo-Pascual et al., 2023; Poch et al., 2018).

In summary, we propose that multiple mechanisms based on voluntary or involuntary shifts of spatial attention to the prioritized item, and on strategic distribution of attentional resources to non-relevant items, might account for different prioritization mechanisms in WM. The oculomotor system seems to be responsible for granting privileged status to the prioritized item, while the maintenance or removal of other items likely depends primarily on strategic resource allocation. As a result, top-down prioritization provides a greater performance benefit than automatic prioritization driven by saccadic preparation.

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Declarations

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Availability of data and materials: The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.